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Lecturer Industrial Attachment for TVET Teachers in Kenya: Access, Challenges, Opportunities

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Abstract

This study investigated the use of Industrial Attachment for vocational teachers (LIA) as part of the professional development of vocational teachers in Kenya. Despite a positive view and a desire to participate in LIA, participation in LIA remains rare with majority of the respondents indicating that they have never participated in LIA or seen their colleagues participate in LIA. Challenges and barriers to LIA include: lack of awareness about LIA, lack of a formal policy to guide LIA, practical challenges such as lack of time and financial facilitation, and the lack of functional linkages between training institutions and industrial firms. Various recommendations to address the challenges are offered.

Keywords

lecturer industrial attachment, continuing professional development (CPD), technical vocational education and training (TVET), vocational teachers, Kenya

1 Introduction

Industrial Attachment for vocational teachers constitutes an important pathway for the professional development of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) teachers. Often referred to as Lecturer Industrial Attachment (LIA) or Teaching Staff Industrial Attachment (TSIA), LIA offers TVET teachers a chance to keep-up-to date with modern work practices and industrial technology (Axmann et al., 2015; Choy & Haukka, 2009; Loveder, 2005). This is especially important in developing country contexts where TVET teachers do not always get a chance to learn and develop an extensive set of technical skills during their training (Grijpstra & Papier, 2015). However, due to limited research on the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) of TVET teachers in developing countries, it is not always clear what views vocational teachers hold about LIA, how frequently they participate in LIA, and what challenges they face in accessing LIA. Research focusing the use of LIA by TVET teachers in developing country contexts would therefore go a long way in supporting the professional development of TVET teachers in developing countries. This study therefore investigated participation in LIA by TVET teachers in Kenya.

As a developing country, Kenya places great emphasis on TVET as one of her solutions to youth unemployment and key to her transition to a manufacturing-based economy. However, a large number of Kenyan TVET teachers lack adequate experience and exposure to industry and modern technology (Ferej et al., 2012; Oketch & Peliwe, 2017; Sifuna, 2020). Recognizing

LIA as an important part of the CPD of TVET teachers, this study therefore investigated participation in LIA by TVET teachers in Kenya focusing on their views on LIA, frequency of participation and challenges faced in accessing LIA.

2 Methods

The study used interviews to supplement a survey on TVET teachers' participation in LIA. The interviews explored the views teachers have on LIA and the factors that hinder or support participation in LIA while the survey focused on how frequently TVET teachers have participated in LIA and their preferred frequency and duration of LIA. Data was collected from 16 interview participants and 170 survey respondents drawn from six vocational training institutes in the Nairobi Metropolitan Area. Thematic analysis of the interviews was then combined with descriptive analysis of the survey data.

3 Findings

Asked for their views on LIA, more than 90 per cent of the survey respondents agreed that LIA constitutes an important learning activity for TVET teachers. In line with this view, 87 per cent of the respondents wished to attend LIA. However, only 40 per cent of the respondents were willing to pay to attend LIA. The data is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1
Views on lecturer industrial attachment

Views on Lecturer Industrial Attachment	Disagree	Neutral	Agree
Industrial attachments are important for TVET teachers.	4.1%	5.3%	90.6%
I wish to attend an industrial attachment for TVET teachers.	4.1%	8.2%	87.6%
I am willing to pay to attend an industrial attachment.	34.7%	25.3%	40.0%

Interview participants also recognized the value of LIA. Benefits for LIA identified included increased confidence and awareness of modern industrial practices, learning new practical skills and improving theory by putting it into practice. Another benefit was the creation of new networks, at the personal, professional and institutional level.

However, despite this positive view and the desire to participate in LIA, LIA remains rare with majority of the respondents indicating that they have never participated in LIA or seen their colleagues participate in LIA. Results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2
Participation in lecturer industrial attachment

Previous participation in LIA	Percentage of respondents (%)
Never	35.9
Once (one time)	29.4
Two or more times	34.7
Total	100

Interview discussions suggested that LIA could be even rarer. Some interview participants were not aware that they could and should attend LIA, while others were unable to distinguish between industrial attachment for students and industrial attachment for lecturers. Thus, some of the survey participants indicating that they had attended LIA may have in-fact been indicating that they had participated in industrial attachment for students or had visited industrial firms to assess their students who were out on industrial attachments.

One given for the low participation rates in LIA was the view that industrial attachment is for students. One teacher indicated as follows: *The thinking is who needs an attachment? The students, they are the ones we teach. For the others, the teacher can keep him or her self up to date by reading on the internet.* [MuTTi_2].

Another reason given was the general of opportunities. Commenting on the fact that she has never participated on LIA and her desire to participate in LIA, one teacher made the following comment: *"I have never gone, but I wish to go. I want to go but there is no opportunity."* [KbTTi_2].

The lack of opportunities to participate in LIA was further linked to the lack of industrial firms and work-places in the catchment areas of the vocational training institutes where teachers work. In addition, there is little or no corroboration between training institutes and industrial firms.

Another reason for the limited participation in LIA was the lack of a formal policy framework to guide LIA and limited facilitation for LIA. Other challenges identified are the lack of time due to heavy teaching work-loads and a school calendar that does not offer extended breaks from school work

With regard to duration and frequency for LIA, various options were given. The suggested frequencies for LIA ranged from once a year to once every three years and durations of one month to six months. From the survey, the most popular preference was once a year for four weeks. The cross-tabulation of the responses for the preferred duration with the preferred frequency is shown in Table 3.

Table 3
Preferred frequency by duration of LIA

		Preferred duration (Number of respondents)				
		Two weeks	Four weeks	Six weeks	Eight weeks	Twelve weeks
Preferred Frequency (Number of respondents)	Every six months	3	7	4	1	0
	Once a year	8	33	8	6	9
	Once every two years	5	11	7	5	9
	Once every three years	2	10	4	5	7
	Once every five years	3	7	0	2	2
	Never	0	5	1	0	3

4 Discussion

The study found that despite viewing LIA as important and therefore wishing to attend LIA, TVET teachers in Kenya lack opportunities to participate in LIA. The study thus supports an earlier finding that TVET teachers in Kenya rarely have the opportunity to participate in Lecturer Industrial Attachment (Sang et al., 2012). This also agrees with prior research findings on TVET teachers elsewhere. For example, in Broad's (2016) study on the CPD practices by Further Education teachers in the UK, only ten per cent of the study participants indicated that they attended industrial placements.

Low participation in LIA was attributed to the view that industrial attachment is for students only, lack of time due to heavy teaching work-loads, and the lack of a framework to guide LIA. For training institutions located away from major industrial hubs, the lack of firms and work-places within reachable distance was a further hindrance. Moreover, the lack functional corroboration between the TVET institutes hinders LIA. This was in agreement with prior studies that have found that vocational training institutions in Kenya generally lack

linkages with industrial firms and other work-places (Kipkogei et al., 2020; Makworo et al., 2013; Wilberforce Manoah Jahonga et al., 2016). In the study by Makworo et al., (2013), linkages involving staff exchange, research collaboration, instructors' industrial experience, and equipment sharing were responded to as non-existent by the survey respondents. In their study on how enterprises support TVET teacher training programs in the western region of Kenya, Kipkogei et al. (2020) found only one firm that offered opportunities for teachers to take up internships.

However, while the lack of linkages may explain low participation in LIA, the lack of LIA may also explain the lack of linkages between firms and training institutions. That is, LIA may serve not just to support teacher learning, it may also serve to support the establishment linkages, both at a personal level and at an official level, between the firms and training institutions. Thus, another good reason to support LIA is to encourage and facilitate liaison between educational institutions and industry.

The barriers and challenges to LIA identified above further agree with findings by Clayton et al. (2005) in Choy & Haukka (2009). They identified resource constraints, such as lack of time and challenges in releasing and replacing teachers when they go professional development; practical challenges such as difficulties in finding workplaces that are willing to host teachers, lack of industries within the reachable distance, organisational impediments such as devaluing of the importance of technical skills, and lack of incentives and policy within the institutions; and dispositional challenges, such as lack of confidence, lack of motivation, and teachers' failure to recognize their own skill deficits.

5 Conclusions

Using a combination of interviews and a survey, this study investigated participation in LIA by TVET teachers in Kenya focusing on their views on LIA, frequency of participation and challenges faced in accessing LIA. TVET teachers in Kenya were found to have a positive view of LIA and a strong desire to participate in LIA, with some teachers willing to pay for LIA. However, despite the positive view, teachers were found to rarely attend LIA. Challenges and barriers to LIA include: lack of awareness about LIA, lack of a formal policy to guide LIA, and practical challenges such as lack of time and financial facilitation.

The very low rates of participation in Lecturer Industrial Attachment (LIA) put to risk the currency and up-to-datedness of TVET teachers' knowledge of modern technology and work processes. Thus, to ensure that TVET teachers in Kenya keep up to date with developments in industry and technology, TVET teachers should be encouraged and facilitated to go for LIA. Apart from visiting the firms for learning purposes, the firms can be avenues of innovation where teachers attempt to use their technical knowledge to solve the technical problems the firms face. Apart from supporting the professional development of TVET teachers, it is noted that LIA may also encourage the development of linkages between firms and training institutions.

The study findings also showed that the lack of functional linkages between the training institutions and industrial firms hinders LIA. It is therefore imperative that technical training institutes are supported to form functional linkages with industries where teachers can attend Lecturer Industrial Attachments. The linkages should be formed in such a way as to encourage collaboration at the level of the teacher, rather than at the level of the institute. Some of the interview participants hinted that the attempts to form such linkages fail because previous attempts have tended to focus at the institute, rather than at the teacher. Further research on this aspect is therefore called for.

Another finding was the lack of time for LIA, and therefore the need to create time for it. Apart from hiring additional teachers to lower the work-load individual teachers have, a reworking of the school calendar to create more time for teachers to participate in LIA and other

forms of CPD is therefore recommended. Since limited participation in LIA was attributed to the lack of a policy framework on LIA, it is recommended that such a policy is developed and implemented. The policy may require TVET teachers to attend LIA every year for four weeks as suggested by the majority of participants.

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Biographical note

Moses Njenga is a PhD candidate at Eotvos Lorand University with an interest in the professional development of vocational teachers. His research explores the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) practices of TVET teachers in Kenya. After his Master's degree in education at the University of Madras in Chennai, India, he held a teaching position Machakos University in Kenya.